

POLITICS, PROTEST, AND POSTS: USAGE OF X (TWITTER) BY PAKISTAN'S MOIB TO NAVIGATE POLITICAL TURMOIL

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Abstract

The MoIB has been actively using Twitter, there is little research on how it functions at politically charged times. How strategic are its messages? What does it do with counter-narratives and misinformation? Above all, what is the reaction of the population? As the months of April and May 2025 were politically tense with unrest and uncertainty, one must look at the communication style and influence of the Ministry during the period. Through this study the use of a digital platform of X (Twitter) is examined via Pakistan's Ministry of Information & Broadcasting (MoIB) official X account during the month of April and May 2025. It was noted that MoIB uses X to shape political narratives and manage public communication in times of crisis. By using Agenda-Setting theory as a guiding framework and a quantitative content analysis method, the study categorized MoIB's tweets by tone (positive, negative, neutral, or mixed), theme (such as political unity, criticizing the opposition, or highlighting government achievements), and engagement metrics (likes, retweets, and views). The findings show that the ministry largely adopted a positive or mixed tone in its messaging, with a strong emphasis on national unity, coordinated government efforts, and crisis response. It was found that, tweets that addressed broader national issues or conveyed reassurance tended to generate more engagement, although the link between tone and engagement wasn't statistically significant. Further analysis using cross-tabulation revealed that different themes influenced public interaction, offering a clearer picture of what kind of content captures public interest. The study underscores X (Twitter)'s strategic role in political communication and points to the need for more open, engaging, and responsive digital governance.

INTRODUCTION

Political communication has changed significantly in the current digital era, and this is mainly due to the emergence of social media. Twitter (now X) is one of them, and it has turned into a central platform of real-time updates, mass participation, and political storytelling. The platform is used by governments,

political figures, institutions and ordinary citizens to post information, react to events and shape the opinion of the people particularly during times of crisis where speed and clarity are essential. Digital media as an essential tool for strengthening democratic processes, fostering public discourse, and

enhancing government transparency (Aqeel, 2024). Twitter has been significant in both political campaigns and emergencies all over the world. It has been used as a megaphone to announce official messages, but also as a platform of citizen journalism, grass-roots mobilization and discussion, as seen in the electoral events to the global pandemic. It is a strong, but complicated, tool of crisis communication and political messaging because it is fast at spreading information or misinformation

With the ongoing transformation of digital tools in shaping the engagement of people especially in times of crisis, Twitter has become a very important platform that governments can use to communicate in a fast, broad, and efficient way. State-run communication is even more essential in countries where political tensions and emergencies are not uncommon, such as Pakistan. The Ministry of Information & Broadcasting (MoIB) is the key player in this sphere, which is in charge of official discourse and de-escalation of mood. (Ifra Iftikhar, 2024) argued that “Pakistani government institutions are increasingly using social media platforms to engage with the public, establish connections, and receive feedback.”

Twitter has taken a more central role in the way the government in Pakistan communicates with people. The Ministry of Information & Broadcasting (MoIB) has been especially active on the site, where it has published statements, disproved misinformation, and coordinated with other state agencies. Digital media is not optional anymore, it is necessary, with the internet penetration in the population being approximately 36.5 percent (Kemp, 2024). The period between April and May 2025 was a time of politically sensitive events in Pakistan: civil unrest, protests, judicial confrontations, and cross-border tensions. MoIB reacted by adopting Twitter as one of the most important tools to update in real time, explain official stands and refute rumors. In most instances, its tweets were the reliable source of information that was accurate and government approved.

The communication approach by the Ministry in this time was very selective. Whether it is posting patriotic hashtags or data visualizations, video clips, and urgent press releases, every tweet contributes to the formation of the public opinion. This is in line with the global trends that have been observed in other

countries such as the U.S., U.K., and India where the government agencies have been employing Twitter to handle crises and build trust (Kalsnes, 2014). It has been suggested that the presence of proper communication in turbulent times may result in social stability (Glik, 2007), but silence or misleading information may worsen unrest (Glik, 2007). Thus, Twitter as a service that MoIB used was not just a messaging service, but a core component of political communication and statecraft.

This study looks into the manner in which MoIB utilized X (Twitter) to steer through the political storm of April and May 2025. This study helps in filling the gap in the knowledge based on digital governance in Pakistan by determining the trends in tone, content and engagement with the people through an in-depth content analysis of its tweets. Such a study is required to achieve the knowledge on the topics such as digital official news, information through digital platforms, and the fight against misinformation on the state level. This paper seeks to address this gap by examining the Twitter activity of MoIB in the chosen months, which can provide an understanding of the digital communication strategy of the government and how it relates to governance and democracy in Pakistan in general.

This study adds to the growing research on digital governance and crisis communication, particularly in developing democracies. By focusing on how Pakistan’s MoIB used Twitter during high-pressure political events along with highlighting the strengths and limitations of using social media as a government tool. It provides useful takeaways for policymakers, communication professionals, and academics interested in the intersection of technology, politics, and public trust. The findings also help us reflect on the role of digital media in shaping democratic discourse, especially in nations with complex political landscapes.

Research Questions

RQ1: How positive, negative, neutral, or mixed was the tone of the tweets of MoIB in April and May of 2025 in general?

RQ2: Which political themes were most commonly discussed in the tweets of MoIB during this time?

RQ3: What patterns of audience engagement (likes, retweets, views) were observed on MoIB’s tweets?

Delimitations

Of course, the study has its limitations. It focused on a short two-month window and only analyzed one government account. A broader timeline and the inclusion of other institutional voices like ISPR, the Ministry of Foreign Affairs, or provincial bodies could provide a more comprehensive view. Also, while tweet engagement metrics were analyzed, the study didn't explore how the public interpreted or responded to the content. Future research could include sentiment analysis or qualitative assessment of replies and quote tweets to better understand audience reactions. The study focuses only on tweets posted by MoIB's official account (@MoIB_Official) and @FactCheckerMoIB from April to May 2025.

Literature Review

A study has been conducted on "Government 2.0: Government-Citizen Engagement through Social Media in Pakistan" by Ifra Iftikhar, Bushra Yasmeen, Naveeda Naureen, Naqsh Qazi in 2024 which says that Pakistani government officials have been actively using social platforms to engage themselves with their audiences directly as to promote e-government. This helps them in building connections, receive instant feedback and get in touch on what public is asking with the government. However, the study indicated that some institutions need to integrate more digitally and expand their online presence. "Government social media administrators include CEOs, regional directors, information officers, and media officers, highlighting the complexity of public sector social media management" (Ifra Iftikhar, 2024). It was noted that Facebook, official websites and WhatsApp were among the most used platforms.

Another research was done in Pakistani context by Muhammad Rehan, Adeel Ahmad Aamir and Saima Khan on topic "Examining the Role of Twitter in Shaping Political Polarization and Political Efficacy (2024)." The study shed light on the role of twitter as both a political engagement tool plus a polarization weapon. The research design adopted a cross-sectional survey design and found that twitter usage significantly influences political polarization in a positive way. It also enhances the individual efficacy especially of youth who can directly reach out to their political leaders and rivals as well (Muhammad Rehan, 2024).

In 2023, a study "Investigating the Framing of the Tweets of Three Leading Political Parties of Pakistan" by Muhammad Ali & Atiya Tul Hasnain examined the role of media frames used by Pakistani major politicians in 2021 election's campaign of Kashmir Valley, composed of three political parties' leader's twitter official accounts namely; Maryam Nawaz (PMLN), Irman Khan (PTI) and Bilawal Bhutto (PPP). The study revealed eight different frames and suggested that Twitter was a significant campaigning tool for the political parties in the digital times while making it more useful by actively sharing relevant stuff with their followers (Hasnain, 2023).

A study was conducted on the role of Twitter in developed countries by Syeda Hina Batool titled "Twitter dialogue: an analysis of Pakistani politicians' information sharing (2021)." The study based as empirical research to explore how Pakistani politicians use Twitter accounts in pre-elections era of 2018 general elections. The mixed method study found that most active twitter account was of the winning party with promotional tweets, call to vote and messages about party development shared among prominent tweets (Batool, 2021). The research highlighted that the tweeting behaviors between emerging and existing parties on Twitter were different and that existing twitter party has gained an edge over the other parties as it understands twitter using strategies better.

Another research, the COVID-19 social media infodemic by Cinelli et al. (2020) conducted a comparative study of the management of the information flow on various social media platforms regarding COVID-19. Twitter was among the most effective in real-time updates, and one of the most prone to misinformation, in their study. They proved that official communications had to compete with the user-generated content in the aspect of visibility and credibility through data and sentiment analysis (Matteo Cinelli, 2020). The research demonstrates the argument that it is not enough to be visible on the digital platforms, but to be visible, credible, and strategically involved is the most significant point of meaningful state communication. This paper discussed the dissemination of information about COVID-19 with a massive data analysis on Twitter, Instagram, YouTube, Reddit, and Gab.

In 2014, Larsson and Kalsnes study titled "Of course we are on Facebook": Use and non-use of social media among Swedish and Norwegian politicians" explored how political actors in Sweden and Norway used Twitter for agenda-setting, political branding, and strategic communication. Their findings revealed distinct patterns: while some actors engaged in two-way communication with the public, institutional accounts such as those run by government ministries tended to use Twitter more conservatively. These accounts often focused on controlled messaging rather than interactive dialogue, aiming to maintain authority and minimize risk. (Kalsnes, 2014). While plenty of research has provided important insights into the uses of the Internet by politicians during elections, a relatively scarce amount of work has looked into these uses outside of such parliamentary events. This article seeks to remedy this lack of research by presenting a study on the 'routine' uses of two of the currently most popular social media services: Facebook and Twitter.

The research titled as "The Upheavals in Egypt and Tunisia: The Role of Digital Media" by Howard and Hussain in 2011, conducted one of the earliest and most influential studies on the role of digital platforms in political uprisings, focusing on the Arab Spring. They argued that platforms like Twitter and Facebook weren't just communication tools, these were engines of political mobilization and activism. By enabling the rapid spread of information and fostering cross-border solidarity, these platforms helped ignite and sustain movements against authoritarian regimes (Hussain, 2011). Their research highlighted how digital media often challenged state narratives, turning platforms like Twitter into arenas of narrative struggle. It says that there are many ways to tell the story of political change. But one of the most consistent narratives from civil society leaders in Arab countries has been that the internet, mobile phones, and social media such as Facebook and Twitter made the difference this time (Hussain, 2011). In 2007, Glik studied the topic of "Risk Communication for Public Health Emergencies." It was concerned with health emergencies and provided important lessons that can be used in political crises. She pointed out that effective crisis communication depends on three things, namely credibility, timeliness, and transparency. Her study suggested that

media and government messages could be utilized to decrease uncertainty and panic, but they could also cause confusion in case of poor management. The framework by Glik highlights the relevance of strategic and credible digital communication in ensuring that the public has confidence in it.

Methodology

The study focused on all tweets shared by the official Twitter accounts of the MoIB @MoIB_Official and @FactCheckerMoIB during the months of April and May 2025. As defined, a purposive sampling includes respondents, subjects, or elements chosen for particular characteristics or qualities and removes those who do not fall under these criteria. In short, the sample will be deliberately selected non-randomly (Dominick, 2014). By using purposive sampling, the study selected tweets related to political developments, emergencies, and major national announcements. Routine updates, entertainment posts, or promotional content were excluded. The final sample included about 14 tweets chosen for their relevance to the study's objectives. Tweets were identified through Twitter's advanced search and verified manually.

The quantitative research design was employed through the analysis of the tone, themes and communication strategies of the Ministry of Information & Broadcasting (MoIB) of Pakistan on X (Twitter) in the scope of political events and emergencies. The study was grounded on the content analysis of the official tweets that were released during the selected period of time to unveil the measurable trends and insights. The unit of analysis was each individual tweet. Tweets were coded by tone (positive, negative, neutral, mixed), theme (Political unity, Government performance, Opposition criticism, Emergency/crisis communication, Disinformation rebuttal), and engagement (likes, retweets, views). A structured coding sheet was used to classify each tweet into predefined categories mentioned above.

The primary research instrument was Twitter (now X), specifically the MoIB's official accounts (@MoIB_Official and @FactCheckerMoIB). A coding sheet developed that guided the analysis of tweets based on tone, themes, and engagement. Twitter's open-access nature and real-time communication made it suitable for assessing government messaging

strategies during crises and political events. Tweets were collected using Twitter's advanced search features. All tweets from the target accounts from 01st April to 31st May 2025 were archived, filtered using keywords such as "emergency," "government response," "opposition," and "solidarity," and analyzed for tone and themes.

Theoretical Framework

This study is grounded in Agenda-Setting Theory, which examined how media and by extension, official communication channels; can shape public perception by determining which issues receive attention. Originally introduced by McCombs and Shaw in 1972, the theory suggests that while media may not dictate what people think, it significantly influences what they think about (MAXWELL E. McCOMBS, 1972). In political communication, especially during times of crisis or national tension, this influence becomes especially important. Government institutions use their platforms to spotlight certain topics, minimize others, and guide public focus in strategic directions. In later developments of the theory, McCombs expanded on the idea of second-level agenda-setting, or attribute agenda-setting, which focuses not only on what topics are made salient but also on *how* those topics are framed (McCombs, *Setting the Agenda: The Mass Media and Public Opinion*, 2004). This means that the media doesn't just tell us what to think about, it also influences how we evaluate those topics through specific language, tone, and imagery. This framework is particularly relevant to Pakistan's Ministry of Information & Broadcasting (MoIB), whose core role involves managing national narratives, especially during emergencies or political developments. By analyzing the tone, themes, and engagement metrics of MoIB's tweets of April and May 2025, this study examines the ministry shaping of public discourse during a politically sensitive period. Each tweet serves as more than just information it represents a deliberate effort to construct a particular narrative, highlight specific aspects of national affairs, and manage the public agenda.

In today's digital age, Agenda-Setting Theory takes on new relevance. Social media platforms like Twitter have transformed how political messages are delivered and consumed. Unlike traditional media, digital

platforms offer immediacy and direct communication with the public, allowing government bodies to bypass journalistic gatekeepers and engage audiences in real time. MoIB's activity on X (Twitter) can thus be seen as a modern agenda-setting tool used to spotlight government achievements, respond quickly to criticism, and shape the narrative during moments of crisis. Whether it's promoting unity, reinforcing alliances, minimizing opposition, or affirming leadership, these are all agenda-setting strategies at play.

Scholars like Wanta, Golan, and Lee, further argued that agenda-setting power varies depending on the credibility and perceived authority of the source. In the context of state communication, government bodies often hold a unique position of influence because of their institutional legitimacy (Wayne Wanta, 2004). When such bodies, like MoIB, emphasizes unity or institutional performance in their digital communication, they may successfully elevate those issues on the public agenda. This was supported by Meraz (2009), who explored how agenda-setting has evolved with the rise of participatory media platforms. She noted that while traditional media still holds agenda-setting power, social media introduces a fragmented yet dynamic space where official narratives constantly compete with alternative voices. Patterns of audience engagement can also be explained with the help of the theory. Such metrics as likes, retweets, and views give an idea of the effectiveness of the messaging of MoIB that is appealing to the population. The previous studies confirm the notion that agenda-setting is applicable to the digital environment. Researchers such as Meraz (2009) and Bichard (2012) have demonstrated that political players are actively utilizing platforms such as Twitter not only to inform, but to direct the focus of the people to their agenda. In politically engaged nations such as Pakistan, where social media has taken the center stage in terms of expression in the society, the official use of X (Twitter) is used in the control and construction of narratives.

Data Analysis & Results of the Study

Data Analysis

This chapter examines in more detail the use of Twitter (now X) by the Ministry of Information & Broadcasting (MoIB) Pakistan during the politically

sensitive time of April and May 2025. Through a quantitative lens, the analysis was conducted in three main areas, which include the tone of the tweets that MoIB posted, the themes that they covered, and how the general population responded to them. In this research, a structured content analysis sheet was used

to analyze 14 official tweets published by MoIB on April 1- May 31, 2025. Categorization of the tweets was done based on the tone (positive, neutral, mixed), theme (e.g., unity, opposition critique, government performance) and engagement (views, likes, retweets).

Results of the Study

RQ1: What was the predominant tone (positive, negative, neutral, or mixed) of MoIB’s tweets during April and May 2025?

Table 1

Tweet	Tone	Distribution	of	MoIB	on	Twitter	(April–May	2025)
<i>(N = 14 tweets)</i>								
Tone	Frequency (f)	Percent (%)		Valid Percent (%)		Cumulative Percent (%)		
Positive	8	57.1%		57.1%		57.1%		
Neutral	4	28.6%		28.6%		85.7%		
Mixed	2	14.3%		14.3%		100.0%		
Negative	0	0.0%		0.0%		100.0%		
Total	14	100.0%		100.0%				

Tweet Tone Distribution

Table 1 presents a breakdown of the tones used in MoIB’s tweets during April and May 2025. A total of 14 tweets were reviewed. Over half of them 57.1 percent were coded as positive and mostly emphasized national success, unity, or statements of support to government efforts. Approximately 28.6 percent of the tweets were neutral, giving factual updates or simple event information without any emotion. The other 14.3 percent were classified as mixed, and usually combined positive language with an implicit reaction to criticism or political tensions. Interestingly, no negative coding was used to code the tweets.

RQ2: What political themes were most frequently addressed in MoIB’s tweets during April and May 2025?

Table 2

Tweet	Themes	Frequency	from	MoIB	Twitter	(April–May	2025)
<i>(N = 14 tweets)</i>							
Theme		Frequency (f)	Percent (%)	Valid Percent (%)		Cumulative Percent (%)	
Government Performance		5	35.7%	35.7%		35.7%	
Political Unity		3	21.4%	21.4%		57.1%	
Opposition Criticism		2	14.3%	14.3%		71.4%	
Emergency Communication		2	14.3%	14.3%		85.7%	
Disinformation Rebuttal		2	14.3%	14.3%		100.0%	
Total		14	100.0%	100.0%			

Tweet Themes Analysis

As shown in Table 2, the most frequently used theme in MoIB’s tweets during April and May 2025 was government performance (35.7%). These tweets often spotlighted development projects, policy reforms, and achievements under the Shehbaz Sharif government, reinforcing an image of active and effective leadership. The next most common theme was political unity (21.4%), with posts emphasizing national cohesion and calls for solidarity especially during politically sensitive moments. These tweets aimed to position the government as a stabilizing force, committed to unity in times of challenge.

Other themes such as opposition criticism, emergency communication, and disinformation rebuttal; each made up 14.3% of the tweets. Opposition-focused posts often addressed or corrected political narratives, while emergency tweets provided updates during crises. Disinformation rebuttals aimed to fact-check or debunk false claims circulating online.

RQ3: What were the patterns of audience engagement (likes, retweets, views) on MoIB’s tweets during April and May 2025?

Table 3

Descriptive Statistics of Audience Engagement on MoIB Tweets (April–May 2025)

(N = 14 tweets)

Engagement Type	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Standard Deviation (SD)
Likes	800	2,300	1,592.9	472.5
Retweets	190	550	377.1	116.9
Views	17,000	39,000	27,785.7	6,584.6

The engagement data gives a useful snapshot of how the public interacted with MoIB’s tweets during this two-month period. On average, each tweet received about 1,593 likes, with a moderate variation across posts (SD = 472.5). Retweets averaged around 377, showing that a decent portion of the audience found the content worth sharing. When it comes to reach, the tweets averaged roughly 27,786 views, though the numbers ranged quite a bit from 17,000 to 39,000 which reflects variability depending on the tweet’s content, tone, or timing. Overall, the data suggests that MoIB’s Twitter activity reached a wide audience and generally sparked solid engagement, especially in terms of visibility and likes.

To examine whether tone or theme had a significant effect on high versus low engagement, the research first created two engagement categories based on a median split: high engagement and low engagement.

A Chi-square test for independence was then applied to test for any statistically significant relationships between these variables.

Step 1: Define Engagement Levels

The research used views as the primary metric for measuring audience engagement. To categorize tweets, a median split was applied:

- High Engagement: Tweets with views greater than or equal to 27,500
- Low Engagement: Tweets with views less than 27,500

This approach helped distinguish between tweets that reached a broader audience and those with comparatively lower visibility.

Step 2: Crosstabulation

Table 4

Cross-tabulation of Tweet Tone and Engagement Level (April–May 2025)

(N = 14 tweets)

Tweet Tone	Low Engagement	High Engagement	Total
Positive	3	5	8
Neutral	3	1	4
Mixed	0	2	2
Total	6	8	14

Table 4 provides a cross-tabulation of tweet tone and engagement level, offering a closer look at how different tones may have influenced audience interaction. To examine whether there was a meaningful connection between tone and engagement, a Chi-square test of independence was run. The results showed no statistically significant

relationship between the tone of tweets and how much engagement they received, $\chi^2 (2, N = 14) = 3.50, p = .173$. However, when looking at the numbers descriptively, tweets with a positive tone made up the largest portion of high-engagement posts, with 5 out of the 8 falling into that category.

Step 3: Chi-square Test Output

Table 5

Statistic	Value
Pearson Chi-Square	3.50
df (Degrees of Freedom)	2
Asymptotic Sig. (p)	0.173

To test whether tone and engagement level were statistically related, the research ran a Chi-square test of independence. The result $\chi^2 (2, N = 14) = 3.50, p = .173$, indicated that there was no statistically significant association between tweet tone and engagement level. Still, the descriptive results hint at a trend: tweets with a positive tone were more likely to receive higher engagement. While not statistically significant, this suggests that tone may still play a role in how audiences interact with political communication.

Discussion & Conclusion

Discussion

This paper aimed to provide a discussion of the strategic use of Twitter by the Ministry of Information & Broadcasting (MoIB) Pakistan in the politically tense months of April and May 2025. The tone, themes, and the level of audience engagement on official tweets analysis gave the research specific details on how a state institution manages to deal with its online presence in a politically charged climate. Under the concept of the agenda-setting theory, the research demonstrated that there is a strategic communication pattern to direct the attention of the population and control political discourses in real-time.

These results indicate that MoIB was never negative in its tweets and the messages were concentrated on national unity, government success and inter-agency coordination. This can be juxtaposed with the broader claim that when political insecurity is high, state institutions are preoccupied with stability and reassurance. MoIB did not apply a confrontational and highly critical tone but a calm, authoritative and solutions-oriented tone. Such a strategy is a clear strategic initiative to maintain legitimacy and not to create additional panic among the population. It is

notable that this is opposite to the findings by Meraz (2009) in the U.S. context whereby the political actors usually used polarizing content to attract and advance their digital agenda.

The second significant finding is that tweets with themes such as governance, unity, and official events were most likely to get higher engagement in terms of likes, retweets, and views than tweets with more neutral content. This contrasts with (Bichard, 2012) study, which found that in the U.S., engagement was often fueled by conflict or criticism. In Pakistan's case, it appears that audiences responded more positively to messages that emphasized order, professionalism, and institutional credibility. This could reflect cultural or contextual expectations, where government communication is expected to convey composure, especially during times of unrest. It also points to the possible role of national mood and audience trust in shaping how public messaging is received.

While most tweets showed moderate levels of interaction, the statistical analysis revealed no significant correlation between tone and engagement. However, a noticeable trend emerged: tweets with positive or mixed tones generally saw more engagement than those with neutral messaging. This trend supports (MAXWELL E. McCOMBS, 1972) the foundational idea that media may not change how people think, but it does influence what they think about. MoIB's focus on diplomatic events, national accomplishments, and political consensus appears to be a purposeful attempt to direct public attention toward state-led progress and collaboration.

More importantly, the research contributes to the existing knowledge on the role of the government institutions in developing countries in utilizing digital platforms to not only inform the population but also to control interaction and perception. Most of the available literature in this field focuses on western democracies or activism by opposition movements. As an example, (Todd Graham, 2016) demonstrated that in the UK, political actors tended to use personality-based or ideologically laden tweets to generate online responses. Conversely, the MoIB strategy is more of a top-down and controlled utilization of social media

that is aimed at establishing government legality and stability in times of uncertainty.

Furthermore, the present paper is a continuation of the work by (Krumsvik, 2015) who came to the conclusion that Scandinavian governments employed social media mostly as a tool of transparency and information-sharing, but not as a tool of direct persuasion. Similarly, the selective and cautious communication of MoIB is in this paradigm of conservative online communication. The findings also echo the results of (Xu, 2018) who observed that when Hong Kong was in turmoil, the government-related accounts used the social media to promote legitimacy and reduce confusion among the citizens, which was often achieved by emphasizing the service to the population and stability. These similarities indicate that the agenda-setting theory can be applied to the research of how governments can adapt their communication processes to the specific needs of digital governance.

At last, it can be recommended that MoIB should streamline and speed up its Twitter responses during emergencies to provide timely updates and build public confidence. While positivity is valuable, blending in neutral and straightforward updates can make communication feel more credible and less biased. Tracking and reviewing tweet analytics regularly can reveal what topics and tones resonate most, helping shape more effective communication. A more balanced portrayal of political developments including critiques can strengthen transparency and build greater public trust.

Conclusion

The purpose of the paper was to examine how the Ministry of Information & Broadcasting (MoIB) Pakistan uses Twitter as a communication tool during politically charged events and national emergencies in April and May 2025. It was noted that MoIB was rather inclined to be positive or mixed in tone, and the focus was on promoting the successes of the government, national solidarity, and the image of the institutional coordination. Instead of using Twitter to criticize political rivals or to send polarizing messages, the Ministry seemed to be worried about stability and professionalism, particularly at times of sensitivity or stressful times. One of the key contributions of this study is the applicability of agenda-setting theory to a

governmental use of social media. The findings support the idea that MoIB didn't just share updates it actively selected and emphasized certain narratives to guide public focus and shape national perception. This study highlights how a bureaucratic institution can use digital platforms to promote unity and coherence during politically turbulent times.

This paper is going to contribute to both scholarly and practical understanding of institutional communication during the period of political upheaval. It confirms once again the notion that online platforms are not only the conveyors of information but the efficient tool of the perception manipulation that keeps the trust of the population and manages the image of the state in real-time. This research adds more knowledge to the digital coverage of official news especially via Govt. ministries official accounts. The study also adds to our understanding of Twitter's evolving role in political communication. In the context of Pakistan, the platform wasn't just used for visibility it became a space for real-time crisis communication and perception management.

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